

Appendix VI

Empirical Results

1: Time spent for analysis (ACH)

2: Time spent for analysis (QBM)

3: Difficulty of the analysis (ACH)

4: Difficulty of the analysis (QBM)

5: The number of relevant beliefs incorporated in the ACH analysis

6: The number of groups (combined beliefs) in the ACH analysis

7: The number of assumptions made in the ACH analysis

8: The number of stakeholders approving the "Avoid ad blockers" goal.

9: The number of stakeholders denying "Avoid ad blockers" goal

10: The number of stakeholders approving the "Block ads while playing games" goal.

11: The number of stakeholders denying the "Block ads while playing games" goal

12: The number of stakeholders approving the "Filter ads" goal

13: The number of stakeholders denying the "Filter ads" goal

14: A goal that should be achieved based on ACH analysis

15: A goal that should be achieved based on QBM